

Emotional-Storyboarding: A Participatory Method for Emotional Designing for Children

Hannah Chung* Elizabeth Gerber**

* *Northwestern University, McCormick School of Engineering
Evanston, Illinois, United States, hannahchung@u.northwestern.edu*

** *Northwestern University, Segal Design Institute
Evanston, Illinois, United States, egerber@northwestern.edu*

Abstract: Emotional-storyboarding is a participatory design method that informs emotional designs for children. When children draw emotional expressions for and craft stories about fictional characters, designers learn how children understand emotion and emotionally evocative experiences. This method overcomes two challenges in participatory design for children—access and verbal communication. We illustrate emotional-storyboarding by presenting a case study of designing a coloring book about overcoming negative emotions. In three hours, we engaged 66 children to create emotional stories using emotional-storyboarding. We also present four guidelines for using emotional-storyboarding to design with children: 1. Face-to-Face crowd-source at children’s events 2. Make storyboarding simple, creative, and active 3. Engage children one-on-one to give them the confidence to express their stories and 4. Publicly praise children’s stories. This case study suggests that emotional-storyboarding can inform meaningful emotional design for children while simultaneously providing children with an immediate positive emotional experience.

Key words: *Children, emotion, co-design, human centered design, participatory design.*

1. Introduction

Emotion influences how people behave, and think when experiencing designed objects, services, and events. Currently, methods such as human centered design and participatory design are used to create emotional designs. Human centered design involves gaining insight into users’ emotional needs by observing people’s lives in everyday context and then testing the ideas directly with users to ensure that their emotional needs are met [1]. Participatory design directly engages stakeholders in the exploratory phase of design to ensure that their emotional (and other) needs are met [2]. Both methods have been effective when designing for and with children to develop objects, services, and experiences such as a software support system for children with cancer [3] and educational art programs [4]. However, the methods remain resource intensive due to the difficulty of gaining access to work with children and their limited verbal ability to communicate their emotional needs to the designers.

To address these challenges, we present a new participatory design activity: emotional-storyboarding. This activity engages children in a simple drawing exercise to express and understand their emotional interests. By allowing children to draw simple facial expressions and then tell stories about the changes in emotion over time, nuanced insights of children’s emotional interests and desires can be elicited. As a method, emotional-

storyboarding is similar to comic-boarding, a participatory design method that uses specially created comic books to generate brainstorming sessions with children [5] and familiar plot formats, interaction styles, and characters in comics. Yet, emotional-storyboarding distinctly relies on children's basic drawing abilities to visually and verbally develop their own emotionally evocative stories. We illustrate emotional-storyboarding by reporting an event in which designers worked with 66 children, ages 5-10 in three hours to gather 66 distinct stories. Based on these stories, we discovered four basic emotions that children most often express and understand: fear, anger, surprise, and happiness. We also learned how they understand the transition between emotions and what elicits an emotional response. From this case study, we present four guidelines for practicing emotional-storyboarding with young children: 1. Face-to-face crowd source at children's events 2. Make storyboarding simple, creative, and active 3. Engage children one on one to give confidence to express their stories and 4. Publicly praise children's stories.

2. Background: Why Design a Coloring Book?

As members of Design for America—a group of volunteers who use design to solve local problems to create social impact, we enrolled in Felissimo's Social Designer competition that called for "imaginative, positive stories and illustrations that translate into fun coloring-in pages for young kids." The competition called for four pages of creative illustrations that children could understand, enjoy, and color. The winning coloring book would be produced and distributed by their non-profit partner, DREAM, an organization that support arts education for underprivileged children.

3. Why Emotional-Storyboarding?

Stories and emotions are intricately connected. People are attracted to and remember emotional evocative stories [6]. People are drawn to stories featuring characters that react with strong emotions to events. And people use stories to communicate strong emotions [14]. But what emotions most interest children and how do they understand and communicate emotions? To answer this question, we turned to the children in our local community. Realizing that children may struggle to talk about emotions out of context, we grounded the discussion in a participatory design activity. We engaged children in emotional-storyboarding, a participatory design method which allows children to design and tell their own emotional stories to inform emotional designs. Collectively, the children's stories informed the design of a single coloring book.

4. Emotional-Storyboarding and the Coloring Book Success

We employed emotional-storyboarding during an annual Halloween event at Northwestern University which attracts approximately 900 children (ages 4-10) from Chicago area to trick-or-treat and play games in a safe environment. This event provided two critical resources for emotional-storyboarding: children and a venue for participatory design work. During this event, we invited the children to participate in a Halloween themed activity called "the Tale of a Pumpkin," in which children choose 4 different colors of pumpkin shapes and draw 4 different emotions on them. We were the only arts activity provided for the children and thus did not compete with another activity of this kind. After children drew 4 different emotions, we glued the shapes on a storyboard and let the children tell us the story of their pumpkin transitioning between emotional states. Finally, we took a photograph of them with their storyboard before they left.

Figure.1 “The Tale of a Pumpkin”: Children drawing on the colored pumpkins and telling stories. Each design facilitator supported one design station (for a total of three stations on one side of a 8x4 ft. table). Each station had 4 pumpkin cut outs, a pack of crayons and markers, and a 2 ft long piece of paper on which to glue the pumpkins. Each child worked alone and took approximately 5 minutes to complete the activity (with one exception of a brother-sister team). The children typically waited no more than 1 minute for an available design station. Parents observed the activity from afar. While 66 children completed the activity, approximately 4 children did not because their parents were leaving the event. Although most children eagerly participated after a brief 10-second explanation of the activity and its purpose, a few children complained that they were not able to draw. We successfully encouraged them to participate by showing them other children’s drawings. When the children were asked to describe the emotions drawn, the most frequently reported four emotions: fear (19%), anger (19%), surprise (18%), and happiness (29%). Additional emotions included confused, sad, and sleepy. The majority of children (61%) chose to start their story with negative emotions and transition to positive emotions at the end. Transitions between emotions typically occurred when other characters entered the story and the main character reacted with physical action. After the event, one designer analyzed the completed stories, the emotions reported, how they were visualized (look of the eyes, mouth, and nose), and the reasons for their character’s transitions between emotions. The final story was a compilation of 66 stories by the children who provided the base story structure that the designer illustrated.

Figure.2 The final coloring book: Titled “Fear. Anger. Surprise. Happiness”

The coloring book was titled “Fear. Anger, Surprise. Happiness” and told a story about a young girl, Mei, who was afraid of the shadow monster and decides to face her fears by opening a door to the unknown. When she opens the door to face the monster, she finds a beautiful world filled with friends who are also courageously conquering their fears. Before submitting the final story to the competition, this story was shown to five children for final review and comprehension. All children understood and enjoyed the story. One month after submission, we received notice that our coloring book won the competition and would be distributed to children worldwide.

5. Emotional-Storyboarding: A Participatory Design Method for Designing with Children

Through the emotional-storyboarding activity, we generated meaningful emotional content to inform the final design. By giving them the freedom to express their creativity, the children became designers. Rather than telling us what emotions interested them, they showed us. Here, by breaking down our participatory methodology, we explain the key components of how to effectively engage children in emotional-storyboarding to generate empathetic content.

5.1 Face-to-Face Crowd-Source at Children's Events

Face-to-Face crowd-sourcing, or bringing large numbers of people to contribute to a project at local events, allows designers direct interaction with a diverse set of children. Designers can get immediate consent from parents and gather many insights in a short period of time. Children can be hard to access without extensive, special permissions. Designers may be able to go to a public playground or children's museum, but these settings don't often allow for focused attention on a participatory design activity due to the distracting setting with uncooperative weather or competing similar activities, respectively. Many designers rely on generous teachers or parents who allow them to visit their classrooms/homes. However, these experiences limit the number of children that can be accessed at one time. Community event planners often welcome additional activity planners to provide a more rich experience for attendees. Using a holiday event also gives the theme for the activity work, here a Halloween theme. Children are meant to participate in this event, and having a fun activity wins their attention. This face-to-face crowd-sourcing approach is a variation of designers' recent efforts to crowd-source on line, testing products and services [7] and generating solutions [8,9] in a distributed network of individuals to reduce monetary and time costs. The primary distinction is that face-to-face crowd-sourcing occurs face-to-face with people, in this case, children. Online crowd-sourcing remains limited to the adult population because of laws related to communicating with children online.

5.2 Make Emotional-Storyboarding Simple, Creative, and Active

To be consistent with participatory design methods that engage children through games [10], we recommend that emotional-storyboarding engage children creatively and actively to attract them to the activity and maintain interest. Our emotional-storytelling activity, "The Tale of a Pumpkin," engaged children to create their own story through simple drawings. Rather than emphasizing the activity rules, we offered familiar drawing materials and a simple task to draw emotional expressions, giving the children the freedom to express their creative ideas. Because they were creating something that was their own, children were attracted to the activity and spent more time at the activity than at other activities at the event which while entertaining, engaged children in one-way interactions (ex. a Halloween Game). In contrast, we asked the children to actively create the content. Because it was easy to see the activity and once done, participants walked around with an artifact from the activity (the storyboard), recruitment to the event occurred naturally after the initial recruitment of two sets of friends. Our activity not only inspired the children but also pleased their adult supervisors who enjoyed watching their children express their creativity and receive validation from peers and non-parental facilitators. Most children remained intently focused on the activity through to completion. For the handful of children who had difficulty focusing, facilitators broke the activity down into discrete tasks, encouraging and praising the children after each drawing completed. This approach to engaging children in creative and active storytelling parallels the whole language approach to literacy. Following the whole language approach, children learn to write by dictating stories to teachers who transcribe their stories on paper. Children are motivated to read when seeing their own stories written down [11]. Similarly, we validated the children's ideas and motivated participation by formally capturing their stories.

5.3 Engage Children One-On-One to Support Stories and Encourage Feelings of Individual Worth

Emotional-storytelling efficiently allowed the facilitators and children to engage in an open conversation, feeling free to exchange ideas about positive and negative emotions safely. Children appeared comfortable talking about the emotional experience of a fictional character, rather than being the focus of the conversation. Introverted children tended to look at the character when telling the story whereas extroverted children tended to look at the facilitator. Our approach to engaging children one-on-one to elicit emotionally inspired stories is related to play therapy, a therapeutic practice designed to help children express their experiences and feelings through self-guided play [12]. During a play therapy session, children are given toys to express their feelings and therapists observe the children at play in an emotionally safe environment. Like with the pumpkins, children may name the toys and give them personal and social histories that resemble their own lives. Play therapy and emotional-storyboarding are based on the belief that play is a natural medium for children's self-expression; however emotional-storyboarding is less concerned with therapeutic outcomes and more concerned with creative expression.

5.4 Publicly Praise Children's Stories.

When children held up their storyboard for the final picture and told their stories to the facilitator, they expressed pride and satisfaction at showing off both their visual creation and Halloween costume. After the photographs were taken, they were congratulated and asked to take their storyboard as a reminder of their creative ability to verbally and visually tell stories. Unlike the candy they received at the same event, we observed children mindfully walking around with their uniquely crafted storyboards throughout the remainder of the event. Children may be incentivized to fully participate in a participatory design activity if they invited to design artifacts that they can take with them and show to others.

6. Discussion

While emotional-storyboarding overcomes challenges such as limited access to children and miscommunication between adult designers and children, it does also pose challenges. For example, as noted, this particular method does require multiple facilitators to manage the large number of participants. Identifying well attended public events for children and integrating emotional-storyboarding activity into the event requires research and permission from organizers who will want to understand how the proposed activity supports the event's mission. During the event, when encouraging children to express emotions, activity facilitators must provide a safe space in which all feelings are warranted. While emotional-storyboarding affords a large number of children to participate, it is difficult to know prior to the activity whether the children will represent the precise demographic for which the designer is designing. In this case, we suspect that not all of the children who participated were necessarily those targeted by the DREAM organization.

Children interested in crafts may be naturally attracted to emotional-storyboarding. In this case, when the goal was to design a coloring book, understanding these particular children's interests is appropriate, however if the goal was to design an emotionally engaging puzzle, the children attracted to puzzle play may not necessarily be the same as those attracted to craft activities. While the case study describes how emotional-storyboarding is used for generating compelling narratives for children, modification may be necessary for designing other products and services for children. For example, imagine how designers interested in engaging children in a participatory design of a new restaurant may modify this method. Facilitators may ask children to draw four

desirable emotional expressions on paper cutouts of a child and then tell a story of what causes a child to progress from one emotional state to the next while eating at a new restaurant. These insights may inform the design of new service elements. This modification blends emotional-storyboarding with Spraragen's expressive service blueprinting [13], a method currently used by service designers to chart the emotive quality of services. To our knowledge, expressive service blueprinting is primarily used with adult users to understand desired and actual emotions experienced during a service. Despite the challenges and possible modifications for different outcomes, we believe that the benefits of this method outweigh the costs when designing emotional children products that reflect their thinking processes and empathetic interests.

7. Conclusion

We present emotional-storyboarding, a participatory design method that engages children in a simple drawing exercise to express and understand their emotional interests. Through a design case study, we present four guidelines for emotional-storyboarding with young children: 1. Crowd source at children's events 2. Make storyboarding simple, creative, and active 3. Engage children one-on-one to support stories and feelings of individual worth and 4. Publicly praise children's stories. The winning coloring book and popularity of the process by which the outcome was achieved suggest that emotional-storyboarding informs meaningful emotional design for young children while providing children with an immediate positive emotional experience. The method builds on an increasing number of design research methods designed explicitly for children. As the number of products, services, and experiences exclusively designed for children increases, a broader range of such methods is needed.

8. Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Design for America members and the children participants for facilitating the emotional storyboarding workshop.

9. Reference

- [1] Kelley, T., Littman, J. (2001) *The Art of Innovation: Lessons in Creativity from IDEO, America's Leading Design Firm*. Broadway Business
- [2] Namioka, A. & Schuler, D. (Eds.), (1993) *Participatory design. Principles and practices*. Hillsdale NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [3] Ruland, C., Starren, J., Vatne, T. (2008), Participatory design with children in the development of a support system for patient-centered care in pediatric oncology. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 41, 4.
- [4] Roussou, M., Kavalieratou, E., Doulgeridis, M., (2007) Children designers in the museum: applying participatory design for the development of an art education program. **IDC '07: The 6th international conference on Interaction design and children**
- [5] Moraveji, N., Li, J., Ding, J., O'Kelly, P., Woolf, S. (2007) Comicboarding: using comics as proxies for participatory design with children. **CHI '07: The SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems**
- [6] Heath, C. & Heath, D. (2007) *Made to Stick*. New York. Random House.
- [7] Kittur, A. Chi, E. Suh, B. (2008) Crowdsourcing User Studies With Mechanical Turk **CHI'08: The SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems**

- [8] Brabham, D. (2008) Crowdsourcing as a Model for Problem Solving. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*. 14(1) 75-90.
- [9] Howe, J. (2008) *Crowd Sourcing: Why the Power of the Crowd is Driving the Future of Business*. Crown Publishing, New York
- [10] Muller, M., Wildman, D., White, E., (1994) Participatory design through games and other group exercises. **CHI '94**: Conference companion on Human factors in computing systems, Boston, MA.
- [11] Smith, F. (2004) *Understanding Reading: A Psycholinguistic Analysis of Reading and Learning to Read*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, New Jersey. Sixth Edition
- [12] Axline, V. (2002) *Play Therapy*. Elsevier Science Limited. London.
- [13] Spraragen, S. (2009) Expressive Service Blueprinting Charting the Emotive Qualities of a Service Experience. Art & Science of Service Conference 2009, Bentley University
- [14] Collins, R. & Cooper, P. *The Power of Story*. Waveland Press. Long Grove, IL.